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and cation exchange capacity of 27.9 cmol (P⁺) kg⁻¹. Three irrigated, transplanted rice genotypes were used: ASD16 (short bold grains), ADT36 (medium grains), and ASD20 (long slender grains). SPAD readings were made at 15, 21, 35, 49, and 56 d after transplanting (DAT), and N was applied when mean SPAD readings fell below predefined threshold levels. In 1997, SPAD threshold values were set as recommended by Balasubramanian et al (1999): at 32 for early growth stages until 35 DAT (when weather was cloudy) and at 35 for later growth stages after 35 DAT (under sunny conditions). Based on observations from the 1997 experiment, a higher threshold value of 37 was fixed for the experiment in 1998. N was applied as prilled urea in dosages of 30 kg ha⁻¹ at 15, 21, 35, 49, and 56 DAT and in a dosage of 45 kg ha⁻¹ at 35 DAT.

The three rice genotypes required different timings and amounts of N application (see table). The first SPAD readings at 14 DAT showed that all three genotypes required N application in both years. This indicates the poor native N supply from this soil. ASD16 required only two N topdressings (60–75 kg N ha⁻¹) in the early stages (i.e., until 35 DAT). ADT36 required N application until 49–56 DAT, while ASD20 needed four to five N topdressings from 14 DAT until flowering. ADT36 and ASD20 required more N application at the reproductive stage (from panicle initiation to first flowering) than at the vegetative stage.

Grain yield and partial factor productivity of applied N (PFP-N = grain

Amount of N applied, grain yield, and partial factor productivity of N (PFP-N) for three rice genotypes^a in an on-station SPAD-N management trial at TNAU farm, Coimbatore, India, 1997 and 1998 wet season (WS).^b

	Amount of N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)						Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	PFP-N
	15 DAT	21 DAT	35 DAT	49 DAT	56 DAT	Total		
1997 WS: SPAD threshold = 32 (early cloudy period) and 35 (later sunny period)								
ASD16	30	–	45	–	–	75	5.1	68
ADT36	30	–	45	–	30	105	5.4	52
ASD20	30	–	45	30	30	135	5.7	42
1998 WS: SPAD threshold = 37								
ASD16	30	30	–	–	–	105	6.4	61
ADT36	30	–	45	30	–	105	6.2	59
ASD20	30	30	45	30	30	165	6.2	38

^aAll three genotypes have 110-d duration. ^bPanicle initiation occurred at 36 days after transplanting (DAT) in 1997 and 42 DAT in 1998.

yield divided by total N applied) were higher in 1998 than in 1997 for all three genotypes. ASD16 was the most efficient genotype, requiring only 75 kg N ha⁻¹ in 1997 and 60 kg N ha⁻¹ in 1998, compared with ADT36 (105 kg N ha⁻¹ in both years) and ASD20 (135 kg N ha⁻¹ in 1997 and 165 kg N ha⁻¹ in 1998). No significant differences in grain yield among all three genotypes, however, were observed in both years. PFP-N of ASD16 was 63% higher than that of ASD20 in 1997; it was more than double in 1998. This indicated that ASD16 is highly efficient in using native and applied N and that this variety could possibly induce nonsymbiotic N₂ fixation in the rhizosphere. Further in-depth studies are required to explain ASD16's high NUE.

The findings indicated that SPAD threshold values should be adjusted according to the responsiveness of

genotypes to applied N and to exploit the yield potential of different rice genotypes. The study also showed that genotypes with coarse grains required lesser N than varieties with finer grains when fixed SPAD threshold values were used. Rice cultivars with fine grains appear to demand more N during the reproductive phase than during the vegetative phase. Further testing of more genotypes, however, is needed to confirm observations.

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Effect of planting density on chlorophyll meter-based N management in transplanted rice

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The chlorophyll or SPAD meter is a promising tool for adjusting the rate and time of nitrogen (N) application for different rice fields. The SPAD technique

ensures N supply to the crop when there is demand for N and results in higher N use efficiency (NUE) (Peng et al 1996, Juliardo and Abdulrachman 1997,

Balasubramanian et al 1999). The exhaustion of soil N supply, however, would depend on plant population. This study examines the effect of planting

density on the SPAD method of managing N in rice.

Two field experiments were conducted to find out the variation in time and quantity of N application under different planting densities by using the SPAD method. The trials also examined the effect of basal N supply through green manure (*Sesbania rostrata*) and urea on later N requirements of crops with different planting densities. Experiments were conducted in the 1998 and 1999 dry seasons (DS, kuruvai, June-September) using rice variety ASD18 at the TNAU wetland farm. Sowing, transplanting, and harvesting dates of the crop were the same in both years. Trials were located in two different fields of the same farm in 1998 and 1999. The soils of the two fields differed mainly in organic carbon and KMnO_4 -N contents (Table 1).

A split-plot design with three replications was used. Three planting densities (33, 66, and 100 hills m^{-2}) served as main plots and five N regimes (zero N, control; *Sesbania* green manure, SGM, at 6.2 t ha^{-1} + 150 kg N ha^{-1} ; SPAD-guided N topdressing, SPAD-N; basal N 25 kg ha^{-1} + SPAD-N; and SGM at 6.2 t ha^{-1} + SPAD-N) served as subplots. Fertilizer N was applied as prilled urea. For the SGM + 150 kg N ha^{-1} treatment, the additional 150 kg N was applied in four splits—i.e., 25% at 7 d after transplanting (DAT), 50% at active tillering (21 DAT), 50% at panicle initiation, and the remaining 25% at 10 d after panicle initiation. In all SPAD-N treatments, SPAD readings were taken at 7-d intervals starting from 14 DAT until first flowering using the youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. Topdressing of N was done whenever the average SPAD reading fell below the threshold value of 37.

Different planting densities required different amounts of N in SPAD-guided treatments (Table 2). The trend of N required for the SPAD method under different planting densities was the same in both soil-years. For the three SPAD treatments, the amount of N required for 33 hills m^{-2} was less than that needed for other densities. For the SPAD treatment

without basal N application, the quantity of N required was the same for both 66 and 100 hills m^{-2} densities. In the 25 kg basal N + SPAD-N treatment, the amount of N required for 100 hills m^{-2} was less than that for 66 hills m^{-2} in both years, probably due to better exploitation of native and applied N by the roots. When SGM was used as basal N, however, the amount of mineral N topdressed with the SPAD method increased with planting densities. The total quantity of N applied was higher in field 2 in 1999 than in field 1 in 1998 for all three SPAD treatments, probably due to lower organic matter and available soil N contents in field 2 (Table 1). This indicates that the SPAD technique can differentiate the plant N requirement of crops grown in soils with different available N status (field 1 vs field 2).

The partial factor productivity of applied N (PFP-N) is calculated as the grain yield divided by the amount of N applied. Pooled analysis of the data for the two soil-years (field 1 of 1998 and field 2 of 1999) showed that the grain yield and PFP-N were significantly higher in field 1 in 1998 than in field 2 in 1999 at the 5% probability level (Table 3). Planting densities of 66 and 100

hills m^{-2} resulted in significantly higher grain yields than the planting density of 33 hills m^{-2} . Since the amount of N applied under the SPAD method was, however, less in 33 hills m^{-2} , the PFP-N was significantly higher in 33 hills m^{-2} than in the other two densities. Earlier, Paraye et al (1996) reported significantly higher grain yield in plots with close spacing (15 × 10 cm) than in those with wide spacing (15 × 20 cm).

Although the mean grain yield did not vary significantly between N treatments, PFP-N differed significantly; a high of 58.2 kg grain kg^{-1} N was observed for SPAD-N, whereas the lowest value of 32.4 kg grain kg^{-1} N was noted for SGM + 150 kg N (Table 3). This showed that the SGM + fixed application of 150 kg N ha^{-1} was the least efficient in nutrient use mainly due to the high level of total N applied. The benefit of need-based N application by the SPAD method was evident in all three SPAD treatments.

The interaction of soil-year and density was not significant for grain yield but was significant for PFP-N (Table 3). The PFP-N for the 33 hills m^{-2} density was significantly higher than that for the other

Table 1. Soil characteristics of the two fields used for the trials in 1998 and 1999.

Soil characteristic	Field 1 (1998)	Field 2 (1999)
Texture	Clay	Clay
Soil pH (water)	7.9	8.1
Electrical conductivity (dS m^{-1})	0.4	0.5
KMnO_4 -extractable N (kg ha^{-1})	214	163
Olsen P (kg ha^{-1})	16	13
NH_4OAc -extractable K (kg ha^{-1})	400	425
Organic C (Walkley and Black 1934) (g kg^{-1})	16.3	5.7

Table 2. Total N applied (kg ha^{-1}) in the different N management treatments and planting densities. Dry season: June-September, 1998 and 1999, TNAU wetland farm, Coimbatore, India.

Planting density (hills m^{-2})	Total N applied (kg ha^{-1})							
	SGM ^a + 150 kg N		SPAD-N		Basal N + SPAD-N		SGM ^a + SPAD-N	
	1998	1999	1998	1999	1998	1999	1998	1999
33	193	201	90	105	85	130	73	126
66	193	201	105	135	130	160	118	156
100	193	201	105	135	100	145	148	171

^aQuantity of total N supplied through 6.2 t (fresh weight) of green manure (*Sesbania rostrata*) was 43 kg in 1998 and 51 kg in 1999.

Table 3. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹), partial factor productivity for applied N (PFP-N), and agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) for the different N regimes under different planting densities. June-September, dry season, 1998 and 1999, TNAU wetland farm, Coimbatore, India.^a

Planting density (hills m ⁻²)	N regimes																			
	Zero-N control			SGM ^b + 150 kg N			SPAD-N			Basal N + SPAD-N			SGM ^c + SPAD-N			Net mean		Net mean		
	1998	1999	Mean	1998	1999	Mean	1998	1999	Mean	1998	1999	Mean	1998	1999	Mean	1998	1999			
																Field 1	Field 2			
Grain yield (t ha⁻¹)																				
33	5.6	2.9	4.3	7.0	5.4	6.2	6.8	5.1	6.0	6.7	4.7	5.7	6.5	5.1	5.7	6.5	4.6	5.6	b	
66	5.8	2.8	4.3	7.2	6.0	6.6	7.1	5.9	6.5	7.6	6.3	6.9	7.1	5.7	6.4	7.0	5.3	6.2	a	
100	6.2	2.9	4.5	6.8	5.9	6.4	7.3	5.9	6.6	7.4	6.3	6.8	7.8	5.9	6.8	7.1	5.4	6.2	a	
Mean	5.9	2.9	b	6.9	5.8	b	7.1	5.6	b	7.2	5.8	b	7.1	5.6	b					
Net mean			4.5	b		6.4	a		6.4	a		6.5	a		6.3	a	6.7	a	5.1	b
PFP-N (total grain yield per kg of N applied)																				
33				36.3	26.7	31.5	75.8	48.5	62.2	78.1	36.4	57.6	87.1	40.6	63.8	69.5	38.1	53.8	a	
66				37.2	29.8	33.5	67.9	43.4	55.7	58.1	39.2	48.6	60.1	36.7	48.5	55.9	37.3	46.6	b	
100				35.1	29.4	32.3	69.3	4.39	56.6	74.2	43.1	58.7	52.6	34.4	43.5	57.8	37.7	47.8	b	
Mean				36.2	28.6	b	71.0	45.3	b	70.3	39.6	b	66.6	37.2	b					
Net mean						32.4	d		58.2	a		54.9	b		51.9	c	61.1	a	37.7	b
AEN (additional grain yield over control per kg of N applied)																				
33				7.4	12.1	9.7	13.7	20.6	17.2	13.0	13.9	13.45	10.5	17.3	13.9	11.1	16.0	13.6	a	
66				7.0	16.0	11.5	12.4	22.7	17.6	13.2	21.8	17.5	10.7	18.9	14.8	10.8	19.9	15.4	a	
100				3.1	15.2	9.1	10.5	22.8	16.6	12.4	23.4	17.9	10.8	17.9	14.2	9.2	19.8	14.5	a	
Mean				5.8	14.4		12.2	22.0		12.9	19.7		10.7	17.9						
Net mean						10.1	c		17.1	a		16.3	ab		14.3	b	10.4	b	18.5	a
Pooled analysis																				
Source of variation	Grain yield						PFP-N						AEN							
	SED ^c		LSD (5%)				SED		LSD (5%)				SED		LSD (5%)					
Soil-year (SY)	0.16		0.36				1.42		3.27				1.34		3.08					
Density (D)	0.19		0.44				1.74		4.01				1.64		ns					
Nitrogen (N)	0.15		0.31				1.33		2.70				1.34		2.73					
SY × D	0.27		ns				2.46		5.67				2.31		ns					
SY × N	0.22		0.44				1.88		3.82				1.81		ns					
D × N	0.27		ns				2.31		4.68				2.33		ns					
SY × D × N	0.37		ns				3.26		6.62				3.29		ns					

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at LSD (5% level). ^bGreen manure (*Sesbania rostrata*). ^cSED = standard error; LSD = least significant difference, ns = not significant.

two densities in field 1 with higher available soil N in 1998. In N-rich soils, the better early growth and tillering would have compensated for the lower planting density in 1998. In field 2 with lower native N supply (1999), the PFP-Ns of all densities, however, were on a par, indicating the need for higher external N supply under all planting densities.

The interaction of soil-year × N treatment was significant for both grain yield and PFP-N (Table 3). Grain yields under all N regimes were significantly higher in 1998 (field 1) than in 1999 (field 2). In 1999 (field 2), PFP-N was significantly higher for SPAD-N without basal N application than with 25 kg N ha⁻¹ or SGM as basal N application. But in 1998 (field 1), PFP-N was not significantly different among the three SPAD treatments. This showed that, in field 2, even with low N

fertility in 1999, basal N application in the mineral or organic form did not improve NUE.

The interactions of density × N and soil-year × density × N were not significant for grain yield but were significant for PFP-N. The PFP-N in different N regimes differed significantly between 1998 (field 1) and 1999 (field 2). There were no significant differences in PFP-N for different densities under different N regimes in 1999 (field 2). But in 1998 (field 1), the PFP-N decreased significantly with increasing density where basal N was applied through prilled urea or SGM.

Pooled analysis of the data on agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) showed significant differences only for means for the soil-year and N regimes (Table 3). The AEN was significantly higher in 1999 (field 2) than in 1998 (field 1),

mainly due to the very low control yield in N-deficient soil of field 2. This also indicated a higher crop response to applied N under low soil N supply in field 2 (1999). Significant differences occurred among N regimes. The basal N (in mineral form) + SPAD-N was on a par with SPAD-N without basal N and SGM + SPAD treatments. The data again showed the superiority of the SPAD method without basal N over the application of basal N in organic form (SGM).

The SPAD method is highly efficient for flooded rice, irrespective of basal N application in mineral or organic form in the clay soils of the TNAU farm. With the fixed SPAD threshold value of 37, the N requirement of rice crops varied with planting density. Further research is needed to standardize SPAD values for different planting densities in rice.

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Evaluation of N management practices for irrigated transplanted rice in Pondicherry, India

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Insufficient and inappropriate fertilizer nitrogen (N) management may account for one-half to two-thirds of the gap between actual and potential yields. About two-thirds of India's rice soils are deficient in available N (Mahapatra et al 1985). Agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) in rice dropped from 16.8 in 1970-71 to 6.6 in 1989-90. Therefore, emphasis is placed on improving N use efficiency (NUE) in rice.

Optimal N management strategies aim to match fertilizer N supply with actual crop demand, thus reducing N losses and maximizing crop N uptake (Thiyagarajan 1997). The chlorophyll or SPAD meter can be used to monitor crop N status and to determine the right time for applying N on rice crops (Peng et al 1996, Balasubramanian et al 1999). The critical SPAD value below which N needs to be applied may vary with cultivar, season, planting density, and soil and plant nutrient status other than N (Balasubramanian et al 1999). Therefore, critical SPAD values have to be adjusted for specific crop-growing conditions.

Controlled-release fertilizers release nutrients at rates and concentrations that match the needs of plants at specific growth stages for maximum efficiency (Shoji and Gandeza 1992). To improve NUE, we evaluated the SPAD method and controlled-release urea (CRU) along with

local N management practices in on-farm trials in Pondicherry, India, in 1998.

Four field trials each were conducted in the 1998 dry season (DS, navarai: January to May) and wet season (WS, sornavari: June to September). Rice variety ADT37 (semidwarf) was used in the DS, and Chinna Ponni (improved local variety) in the WS. Treatments included a zero-N control, SPAD-guided N application, 20 kg N ha⁻¹ basal + SPAD-guided N application, a single basal application of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ as CRU (with 6% coating), and the farmers' practice of 150 kg N ha⁻¹ applied in three splits (50% basal, 25% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation to flowering). The first four N treatment plots received irrigation water directly from the field irrigation channel. Each plot was surrounded by a good bund. The farmers' fertilizer plot was demarcated with four pegs adjacent to the other treatment plots. All plots received a basal application of 22 kg P and 42 kg K ha⁻¹.

In the SPAD-N treatments, leaf N status was monitored weekly starting from 14 d after transplanting (DAT) until first flowering. The youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot was used for the measurement. Whenever the average SPAD reading fell below the set critical value of 35, N fertilizer was applied immediately. In the DS, the amount of N applied each time was 30 kg

N ha⁻¹ from the early to maximum tillering stage (14–28 DAT), 45 kg N ha⁻¹ from the maximum tillering to panicle initiation stage (29–48 DAT), and 30 kg N ha⁻¹ from the panicle initiation to flowering stage (49 DAT to flowering); it was reduced to 20–30 kg N ha⁻¹ for corresponding stages in the wet season.

Plant height recorded at physiological maturity varied with treatments (Table 1). Height ranged from 91.3 to 93.1 cm for CRU, followed by other treatments. The basal + SPAD-N treatment recorded the most panicles per unit area, closely followed by CRU. The lowest panicle number was recorded in the control.

Among the four N treatments, basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ + SPAD-N produced the highest yield of 5.8 t ha⁻¹ in the DS and 6.3 t ha⁻¹ in the WS. Increased yields in the basal + SPAD-N treatment were mainly due to increased panicle number m⁻². These soils, with a control yield above 4 t ha⁻¹, require basal N application in addition to N topdressing based on observed SPAD values. This contrasts with observations at other sites in India. The CRU treatment recorded the highest straw yield, followed by basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ + SPAD-N.

Gross return was computed based on the prevailing market value of inputs and produce, such as grain and straw. The